

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PREDICTED TIMING OF THE USE OF FIXED DENTURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997518>

Abstract

The success rate of dental treatment is considered high when 95% of orthopedic structures after 5 years and 85% after 10 years of use do not create problems for patients and doctors [3,4]. Clinical cases, which, due to the combination of several possible causes of complications, can be considered diagnostically difficult, deserved a separate analysis - this became the subject of our study.

Keywords: fixed dentures, terms of use, quality assessment.

The purpose of the work is to analyze the clinically important aspects of the expert assessment of the quality and suitability of NZP for use, to determine the appropriate diagnostic formulations and appropriate therapeutic measures.

Materials and methods.

An outpatient dental examination was performed on 104 patients - 58 (55.76%) women and 46 (44.23%) men aged 30-60 years, contacted the clinic of orthopedic dentistry to determine the need to replace or change the design of the IUD. Terms of using stamped, stamped-cast, soldered, solid-cast WIP in 30 (28.84%) people - up to 6 months, in 45 (43.26%) people - from 6 to 12 months, in 15 (14.42%) people - from 12 to 24 months, in 14 (13.46%) people - from 2 to 5 years. The data of anamnesis (according to the problem-oriented scheme), detailed examination of the oral cavity, panoramic radiography, occlusal diagnostics, as well as assessment of the suitability of NZP for use in terms of biocompatibility and surface condition were analyzed [8].

Results and discussion.

Concern or concern of patients that artificial crowns or bridges do not meet the requirements, requests, needs or expectations, accompanied by a variety of

complaints of a local or general nature. In such cases, despite the expected visibility of the "unsatisfactory" (imperfect, unacceptable) state of ILD, the prosthodontist-stomatologist faces special tasks compared to the initial visits of patients [1.2]. Firstly, dental treatment in history, in particular the selection and fitting or the presence of dentures, implants of teeth and jaws, not accidentally recognized by WHO experts as factors affecting the state of public health and access to health care institutions [9]. At the same time, the need for medical care may also be due to other circumstances that are significant in the overall structure of the short or long-term physical, mental and social functioning of

the patient, the influence of which is manifested precisely when using dentures. Conditions such as the formation of somatic symptoms (feeling unwell) for mental reasons - compensatory neurosis, allergies, unspecified, orthopedic devices and related unfavorable cases, other specified conditions after surgical treatment create considerable difficulties for the diagnosis of general medical practitioners. Dentists, unfortunately, are also not always able to recognize the underlying condition that causes the need for medical care, so some complications of dental interventions have remained unspecified. Secondly, the description of the state of dentures provides for a reasoned certification of "fitness for the purpose as a fact of compliance with the established requirements for the ability of the prosthesis to perform a certain function under given conditions" or, conversely, non-compliance. In addition to "nonconformity", for a clear definition of responsibility for manufactured products, non-fulfillment of a requirement related to the intended customer (physician and patient) or specified use is characterized as a "defect" [10]. None of the 104 patients at the time of the examination had a specified diagnosis and, accordingly, a reasoned plan of treatment, which gave grounds for seeking a consultation. Signs of an unsatisfactory condition of the ICD such as a violation of fixation and defects in the design of the restorative material, secondary carious lesions and fractures of the supporting teeth, damage to periodontal tissues, violation of occlusal contacts, inaccurate fit or incorrect formation of the edges of the crowns, as well as local or general adverse reactions are usually associated with significant costs. time, effort and funds to fulfill the main and related medical appointments Along with determining the indications for the use of fixed prostheses, methods of preparing teeth, techniques for making crowns, criteria for their quality and guarantee2, possible tolerances for the quality of manufacturing crowns are provided, taking into account the clinical features of the pathology and the state of the patient system, as well

as the possibility of complications, independent of treatment tactics [11]. Experienced specialists note that the discussion of a preliminary treatment plan with the execution of the patient's voluntary informed consent, as well as the reflection in the contract (agreement) for the provision of dental services, the possibility of certain complications, independent of the quality of the doctor's work, meets the requirements of clinical guidelines, settings and protocols [6].

As you know, one of the criteria for the success of dental orthopedic treatment, according to medical and statistical reporting, is the proportion of cases of replacement of dentures due to "significant shortcomings that exclude or make it unacceptable to use the result of work in accordance with its intended purpose or to eliminate which is required high costs" [5.7].

The indicators of the quality of medical care are satisfaction with the conditions for the provision and results of treatment and the frequency of patient complaints (according to sociological studies), because quality (poor, good or excellent) is the degree to which the totality of its own (constant) characteristics of the product meets the requirements of the consumer [3.4]. Tests and criteria for assessing the quality (good, fair, poor, unacceptable) of artificial crown prosthetics, recommendations for the prevention of adverse events, adjustment or remanufacturing of dentures have already been developed, although they have not yet been widely adopted. According to the results of the examination, crowns of good and satisfactory quality in 23 (22.11%) persons were considered appropriate for the purpose, suitable (recommended) actions - to observe and, if possible, correct, and unsatisfactory and unacceptable quality in 81 (77.88%) persons - inappropriate, unsuitable for applications with recommendations to replace in a planned (prophylactic) manner or without delay.

conclusions

1. To clarify the reason for seeking medical help (the main condition), dentures in the analysis of outpatient examination data should be considered as a structurally and functionally integrated, and not a temporary or isolated part of the dentoalveolar system.

2. Diagnostic formulations indicate the structural and clinical (technological) characteristics of dentures, reactions of the body to dentures or circumstances associated with the use of dentures and affect the state of health, but in themselves are not a disease.

3. Based on the assessment of the level of quality, suitability for the purpose, as well as the suitability of NZP for use / subsequent use for 104 patients, recommendations were made regarding concomitant therapeutic measures: periodic monitoring, adjustment, replacement or design changes. Prospects for further research, in our opinion, are related to development and coordinated implementation of standardized criteria for

assessing the preserved / lost quality of dentures, which is important not only from a clinical, but also from a medical statistical and legal point of view.

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